

ADAPTATION OF SOLID MICROMECHANICS FOR MODELLING CURING RESINS IN PROCESS SIMULATIONS

S. Malekmohammadi¹, R. Thorpe¹, A. Poursartip^{1*}

Composites Group, Depts. of Materials Eng. and Civil Eng., The University of British Columbia

*Corresponding author (anoush@composites.ubc.ca)

Keywords: *Micromechanics, Thermoset Matrix Composites, Prepreg, Rheometry, Processing, Process Modelling*

Abstract

Process modeling has been an increasingly successful strategy for understanding and managing the processing and manufacturing of composite structures. In current generation process models, the flow response phase is dealt separately from the solid response (stress development) phase. As a result, any inconsistency in the representation of material behaviour can be safely ignored. However, recently Haghshenas et al [1] presented an integrated framework for predicting both the flow and stress development in a continuous simulation. For such integrated simulation, it is now necessary to ensure that we have consistent and correct formulations for all material properties from the uncured viscous state to the cured elastic state. One significant issue is that of micromechanics, namely the interaction of the fibre and resin resulting in prepreg or ply level properties. The simplest approach for modeling the behaviour of prepregs would be to incorporate the concept of a fibre bed into classical micromechanics. We introduce the approach in this paper by considering the addition of a fibre bed shear response to classical isostress solid micromechanics. To evaluate the validity of this approach in both pre-gelation and post-gelation stages, rheological and DMA tests were performed on an out-of-autoclave prepreg. Results show promising agreement between the simple model predictions and the preliminary experimental results.

1 Introduction

Processing of thermoset composites involves both resin flow and stress development. Several models have been proposed to predict the deformation of prepregs at each stage. In flow models, the resin and fibre are said to interact through the fibre bed, namely the slight waviness of the fibres within the

prepreg [2]. It was shown by Gutowski et al. [3] that at high volume fractions of fibre ($v_f > 0.5$), the fibre bed plays an important role in carrying the load in the transverse direction due to fibre waviness. Building on this, Cai and Gutowski [4] developed a 3D fibre bundle model to predict the deformation behaviour. From a modelling perspective, this type of response is then coded into flow models, e.g. [5] and the load sharing between fibre bed and resin simulated in order to predict compaction of a composite structure.

Although flow models can predict the behaviour of composites at the early stages of processing, a solid mechanics based model is required to simulate the response past gelation, when residual stresses start to develop, e.g. [6]. In these models, appropriate solid micromechanics equations are needed to calculate the ply level properties based on the continuously changing resin and fibre properties during the cure cycle. As is well known, classical micromechanics exist in a variety of flavours, and there is a significant history of their development and use, e.g. [7]. In this introductory work, it is instructive to use the simple rule of mixtures approach to guide our thinking in identifying the discrepancies, if any, between the fluid and solid regimes. At one extreme, based on the isostrain condition, strains in both resin and fibre are assumed to be identical. The Young's modulus in the fibre direction can then be expressed in terms of the modulus of the phases, E , and their volume fractions v , as:

$$E_c = v_f E_f + v_r E_r \quad (1)$$

The subscripts c , f , and r refer to the composite, fibre and resin, respectively. In shear and in the transverse loading direction, the isostress assumption is more appropriate. Consequently, the composite shear modulus can be estimated as:

$$\frac{1}{G_c} = \frac{\nu_f}{G_f} + \frac{\nu_r}{G_r} \quad (2)$$

Equations (1) and (2), which are shown in classical analog representation in Figure (1), will be used in this paper as the basis for evaluating the behaviour of prepreg early in the cure cycle, when the resin is at a low degree of cure and high temperature. At high degree of cure, the resin behaves as a solid and simple solid isostress micromechanics can be used.

2 Experimental Results

In order to characterize the behaviour during the cure cycle, two types of test were performed on both neat resin and prepreg samples. The neat resin results are used as input to the micromechanics model and the predictions compared to the prepreg results.

A rheometer was used to measure G' (and other properties) from the uncured state to the gelled state. Prior to gelation, a resin can flow, and this is consequently the domain of flow models. A Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA) was used to measure the post-gelation behaviour. Past gelation, resin flow is not possible and as the viscoelastic properties of the resin develop, stress can be carried, and this is the domain of stress development models. Experiments were performed on Advanced Composites Group MTM45-1 out-of-autoclave material at heating rates of 1 and 2 °C/min.

2.1. Rheological Tests

Pre-gelation behaviour was characterized using a TA Instruments AR2000 rheometer. Oscillatory shear tests were performed at a frequency of 1 Hz with the temperature ranging from 50°C until the material had gelled, as past this the point the viscosity exceeded the capacity of the rheometer. Figures (2) and (3) present the viscosity and storage modulus variation through the temperature range, for both prepreg and neat resin.

2.2. DMA Bi-Material Beam Tests

Post-gelation properties of both resin and prepreg were measured using a TA Instruments Q800 DMTA (Dynamic Mechanical and Thermal Analyzer). 3-point bend tests were performed on bi-

material beams (BMB). A BMB consists of a steel shim supporting a layer of prepreg or uncured resin. Samples were prepared by adhering and trimming prepreg or resin film to the steel shim. Experimental procedure and data extraction from the BMB is based on the work of Twigg et al. [8] and Curiel and Fernlund [9]. The effective stiffness of the sample was calculated for each data point using:

$$(E \cdot I)_{Eff} \approx (E^* \cdot I)_{Eff} \cdot \cos \delta = \frac{F \cdot L^3}{48 \cdot y} \cdot \cos \delta \quad (3)$$

where the force (F), displacement (y) and phase angle (δ) are raw data outputs from the DMA, and E and E^* are the storage and complex moduli respectively. The effective stiffness of a bi-material beam can be calculated using [10]

$$(E \cdot I)_{Eff} = \frac{w \cdot t_{sh}^3 \cdot t_c \cdot E_{sh} \cdot E_c}{12 \cdot (t_{sh} \cdot E_{sh} + t_c \cdot E_c)} \cdot K_1 \quad (4)$$

$$K_1 = 4 + 6 \cdot \frac{t_c}{t_{sh}} + 4 \cdot \left(\frac{t_c}{t_{sh}} \right)^2 + \frac{E_c}{E_{sh}} \cdot \left(\frac{t_c}{t_{sh}} \right)^3 + \frac{E_{sh}}{E_c} \cdot \frac{t_{sh}}{t_c} \quad (5)$$

where w is the sample width, t_c is the composite thickness, t_{sh} is the steel shim thickness, E_c is the composite Young's modulus and E_{sh} is the steel shim modulus. Using Excel, a macro was written that utilizes the 'solver function' to solve the value of the composite modulus for each data point. The shear modulus in the 2-3 plane (G_{23}) is then estimated as:

$$G_{23} = \frac{E_2}{2 \cdot (1 + \nu_{23})} \quad (6)$$

where ν_{23} is the Poisson ratio of the composite in the 2-3 plane [7]. During the evolution of the resin from a liquid to a viscoelastic solid, the resin Poisson ratio varies. However, Bogetti and Gilepsie [11] reported no significant sensitivity in macroscopic composite properties by assuming a constant Poisson ratio for the resin. Therefore a constant Poisson ratio (ν_{23}) of 0.59 for the composite and 0.36 for the resin was chosen based on available data in the literature [7]. These values were used to give a lower and upper bound for the extracted shear modulus, and the difference was negligible compared to the effects of interest in this paper.

In order to connect the pre-gelation data from rheological tests to the post-gelation data from the DMA tests, uncured samples were heated in the DMA up to 180°C at the same ramp rates used in the rheological tests. Once at 180°C, the samples were cured at constant temperature for 120 minutes. Figures (4) and (5) present the extracted G' data for MTM45-1 resin and prepreg respectively for experiments run at 1.0 and 0.1 Hz. DMA G' data above 20 MPa is considered to be high confidence data since the contribution of prepreg or resin becomes significant to the BMB effective stiffness. Below this value, the prepreg or resin stiffness contribution is less than 1% of the steel shim which results in a high sensitivity and resulting errors in calculated G' from small uncertainties in the BMB effective stiffness. Examining the G' data from fully cured samples reveals a very accurate prediction for the resin modulus, however, it underestimates prepreg modulus. Underestimation of prepreg shear modulus may be attributed to the lack of debulk during the experiment. By comparing the prepreg thickness from a BMB test to a properly debulked sample, the porosity may be quantified and an adjusted G' based on foam theory may be calculated. Since porosity can change during the curing process, in this preliminary study we merely acknowledge that the reported prepreg modulus is an underestimate.

Overlaying the DMA and rheometry data for the resin shows that the storage modulus develops as a continuous function during the temperature ramp, as shown in Figure (6). In this figure, the zone where there is low confidence in both DMA and rheometer data is marked appropriately, but it is clear that the behaviour is continuous over the gap. Similar behaviour is observed for the prepreg, but not shown for lack of space.

3 Modeling Approach

Direct measurements on prepreg have shown that that fibre bed stiffness values are in the 50 -500 KPa range [12].

Considering Figure (3), the minimum observed value for the resin storage modulus is ~ 20 Pa, whereas the minimum storage modulus of the prepreg is of the order of 100 KPa. However, classical isostress micromechanics (Equation (2))

would predict a value of 50 Pa for the prepreg. There is clearly a significant discrepancy that must be resolved.

Based on the hypothesis presented here, the resin is being deformed along with the fibre bed. Figure (7) represents in schematic form the deformation behaviour of a fibre bed impregnated with resin under shear loading. The fibre bed is represented as a combination of vertical cantilever beams under lateral loads and horizontal straight beams under shear loads. According to this representation, the fibre bed acts in parallel to the resin (isostrain condition), and therefore the simplest approach would be to replace the G_r in Equation (2) with G'_r where G'_r represents the combined effect of resin and fibre bed stiffness $G_r + G_{fb}$ (Equation (7)).

$$\frac{1}{G_c} = \frac{v_f}{G_f} + \frac{v_r}{G'_r} \quad (7)$$

Where G_{fb} is the fibre bed shear modulus, and relates the fibre bed deformation to the effective stress carried by the fibre bundles under shear. As has been shown elsewhere [12], we expect G_{fb} to depend on the fibre volume fraction. Employing simple beam bending theory, G_{fb} can be estimated by Equation (8)

$$G_{fb} = \frac{3 E_{f1} \pi d^3}{64 h^2 \cdot L} \quad (8)$$

E_{f1} is the elastic modulus of the reinforcement fibres in the longitudinal direction, and d , h and L are characteristics of the fibre bed configuration as described in Figure (7). Equation (8) can be written in terms of the fibre volume fraction v_f and maximum available fibre volume fraction, v_a , using the formulation given in Cai and Gutowski [4].

$$G_{fb} = \frac{3 E_{f1} \pi}{64 \left(\frac{h}{L}\right)^2 \beta^3 \left(\sqrt{\frac{v_a}{v_f}} - 1\right)^3} \quad (9)$$

Here β is a parameter describing the amount of fibre waviness used in Cai and Gutowski [4]. As the compaction level increases, more fibres are engaged and the fibre volume fraction reaches its maximum value, v_a . According to Equation (9), for the highest compaction level when all fibres are contacting each other, G_{fb} approaches infinity. To understand the

significance of G_{fb} , a simple analog model is presented in Figure (8). According to this representation, as the fibre compaction level reaches its maximum limit, the fibre element dominates the deformation response of the composite. In other words, the composite deforms mainly due to shear in the wavy fibres. This analog model also implies that under a constant compaction level when the resin is in its fluid state, the fibre bed contribution in the composite modulus becomes significant. As the resin gradually vitrifies, its shear modulus becomes significant and G'_r is dominated by the resin modulus. Therefore, Equation (2) (classical isostress micromechanics) is recovered and Figure (8) is simply regenerated to Figure (1a).

4 Results

The experimental results for prepreg and resin modulus over the full range of response from hot uncured to cold cured are cross-plotted in Figure (9). Overlaid on the experimental results are both Equations (2) and (7). For Equation (7) a value of 62 KPa is used for G_{fb} . This value can be calculated from Equation (8) using $\nu_f=0.6$, $E_{f1}=200\text{GPa}$, $L=20\text{mm}$, $d=8\mu\text{m}$ and $h=110\mu\text{m}$. These are all reasonable values, and the resulting G_{fb} is consistent with previous experimental values [12].

In Figure (9) the highest measured values are shown as the upper bound (red symbols) whilst the lowest measured values are shown as the lower bound (blue symbols). Two vertical dotted lines indicate the region of lower confidence measurements. In the early stages of cure (low resin storage moduli), there is a significant discrepancy between classical isostress micromechanics predictions and the experiments. This difference is due to the contribution of the fibre bed, as demonstrated by the good agreement with Equation (7). As the resin cures (leading to higher resin moduli), the fibre bed contribution becomes negligible and classical micromechanics is recovered, with Equations (2) and (7) giving the same prediction.

Figure (9) shows that by incorporating the properties of the fibre bed into the solid micromechanics equation, the prepreg storage modulus can be predicted even in the early stages of cure where resin is still in a fluid state.

5 Conclusion

In this paper we have shown that a promising approach is to use a simple, but physically based, modification to classical solid micromechanics to predict prepreg storage moduli in the fluid phase. This is an important step in the development and implementation of integrated process models that span the fluid and solid phases of composites manufacturing, as in the work by Haghshenas et al [1]. Preliminary experimental results have been presented, as well as the use of the simplest micromechanics models. In future work, additional experiments for other materials and for other properties (axial and bulk) as well as more sophisticated micromechanics models will be evaluated.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC) for financial support, and Dr. A. Arafath of Convergent Manufacturing Technologies and colleagues in the UBC Composites Group for many stimulating discussions. The provision of the rheometry data by Dr. Pascal Hubert of McGill University is also gratefully acknowledged.

Fig. 1. Simple analog models describing classical micromechanics for (a) Isostress and (b) Isostrain conditions.

Fig. 2. Viscosity variation during temperature ramps at 1°C/min (blue) and 2°C/min (red).

Fig. 3. Shear storage modulus variation during temperature ramps at 1°C/min (blue) and 2°C/min (red).

Fig. 4. Shear storage modulus from DMA bi-material test during cure cycle for MTM45-1 resin.

Fig. 5. Shear storage modulus from DMA bi-material test during cure cycle for MTM45-1 prepreg.

Fig. 6. Shear storage modulus from both rheometer and DMA bi-material tests during cure cycle for MTM45-1 resin at 1°C/min and 1Hz.

Fig. 7. Fibre bed deformation under shear stress. (a) Fibre bed deforms with resin. (b) Fibre deforms under the overall shear stress.

Fig. 8. Modified isostress micromechanics model using the concept of fibre bed shear modulus.

Fig. 9. Prepreg shear modulus versus resin shear modulus for MTM45-1. Model predictions are shown as solid and dotted lines for the modified and classical isostress micromechanics models respectively.

References

- [1] M. Haghshenas, R. Vaziri and A. Poursartip "Integrating the simulation of flow and stress development during processing of thermoset matrix composites". *Proceedings of ICCM-17*, Edinburgh, Scotland, 2009.
- [2] P. Hubert and A. Poursartip "A Review of Flow and Compaction Modelling Relevant to Thermoset Matrix Laminate Processing". *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, Vol. 17, No. 4, pp 286-318, 1998.
- [3] T.G. Gutowski, Z. Cai, S. Bauer, D. Boucher, J. Kingery and S. Wineman "Consolidation

- Experiments for Laminate Composites". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 21, No. 71, pp 650-669, 1987.
- [4] Z. Cai and T.G. Gutowski "The 3-D Deformation Behavior of a Lubricated Fiber Bundle Consolidation Experiments for Laminate Composites". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No. 8, pp 1207-1237, 1992.
- [5] P. Hubert, R. Vaziri and A. Poursartip "A Two Dimensional Percolating Flow Model for the Process Simulation of Complex Shape Composite Laminates". *International Journal of Numerical Methods in Engineering*, Vol. 44, No. 1, pp 1-26, 1999.
- [6] A. Johnston, R. Vaziri and A. Poursartip "A Plane Strain Model for Process-induced Deformation of Laminated Composite Structures". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 35, No.16, pp 1435-1469, 2001.
- [7] C. T. Herakovich "Mechanics of Fibrous Composites". John Wiley & Sons, 1998.
- [8] G. Twigg and A. Poursartip "An Accelerated Approach for Measurement and Modeling of Modulus Development, Cure Shrinkage and CTE Applied to 977-3 Resin" Convergent Manufacturing Technologies internal report, 2003.
- [9] T. Curiel and G. Fernlund "Deformation and stress build-up in biomaterial beam specimens with a curing FM300 adhesive interlayer". *Composites Part A*, Vol. 39, No. 2, pp 252-261, 2008.
- [10] R.J. Roark, "Roark's Formulas for Stress and Strain". ed. Young, W.C., McGraw Hill, New York, 1989.
- [11] T. A. Bogetti and J. W. Gillespie, Jr, "Process Induced Stress and Deformation in Thick-Section Thermoset Composite Laminates". *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 26, No. 35, pp 626-660, 1992.
- [12] P. Hubert and A. Poursartip "A Method for the Direct Measurement of the Fibre Bed Compaction Curve of Composite Prepregs". *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 32, No. 2, pp 179-187, 2001.